

Some Mixed Alkoxy Cyano Derivatives of Titanium(IV) and Zirconium(IV)

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The reactions of Ti(IV) and Zr(IV) alkoxides, $M(OR)_4$ (where $M=Ti, Zr$; $R=Et, Pr^i$) with pyruvitrile have been carried out. The products of the type $M(OR)_{4-n}(CN)_n \cdot m CH_3COOR$ (where $n=1, m=0$; $n=2, m=0.5$; $n=3, m=1$; $n=4, m=1.5$ (for $M=Ti$) or 2 (for $M=Zr$) have been isolated. The reactions of metal tetracyanide derivatives with isopropanol have also been studied. Attempts have been made to throw light on the nature of these derivatives on the basis of their molecular weights and i. r. spectra.

A number of halide alkoxides of titanium(IV) and zirconium(IV) have been synthesised by the reactions of their alkoxides with acetyl halides¹⁻⁶. The alkoxy isocyanato derivatives of titanium⁷ and zirconium⁸ have also been synthesised by the reactions of their isopropoxides with acetyl isocyanate. Recently, alkoxy cyanides of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) have been synthesised by the reactions of their alkoxides with pyruvitrile⁹.

In view of these results, it was considered of interest to carry out the reactions of titanium(IV) and zirconium(IV) alkoxides with pyruvitrile.

Results and Discussions

The reactions of titanium(IV) alkoxides with pyruvitrile found to be exothermic in nature. Cyclohexane was chosen as a suitable solvent because it forms azeotrope with the esters produced in the reactions. These reactions may be represented by the following general equation:

(where $n=1, m=0$; $n=2, m=0.5$; $n=3, m=1$; $n=4, m=1.5$ and $R=Et$ or Pr^i).

The monocyano derivative, $Ti(OPr^i)_3(CN)$ is semi-solid in nature and is soluble in common organic solvents while other alkoxy cyano derivatives are solids, soluble in acetone and insoluble in other common organic solvents. The tetracyano derivative $Ti(CN)_4 \cdot 1.5CH_3COOPr^i$ is soluble even in acetone.

Molecular weight determination of $Ti(OPr^i)_3CN$ shows a complexity of the order of 2.5 in refluxing benzene. Molecular weights of di- and tri-cyano derivatives measured in acetone suggested a tendency of slow dissociation to a monomeric form.

As depicted by the infra red spectra the alkoxy cyano derivatives associate mainly through alkoxy bridges but weak association through cyanide bridges is also indicated. The lower solubility tendency of the higher cyano derivatives thus appears to be mainly due to more ionic character of the bonds coupled with their weak association in the solid state through cyanide bridges (which tend to get broken in polar solvents like acetone).

All the alkoxy cyano derivatives of titanium on being heated under reduced pressure disproportionate to give their alkoxides.

The reactions of crystalline $Zr(OPr^i)_4 \cdot Pr^iOH$ with pyruvitrile in different molar ratios under refluxing conditions gave products with $CN:Zr$ ratios lower than expected. This might be due to the competitive reaction tendency of the adduct with pyruvitrile at higher temperature. The reactions were, therefore, repeated at the room temperature. On leaving an equimolar mixture of $Zr(OPr^i)_4 \cdot Pr^iOH$ and CH_3COON overnight, $Zr(OPr^i)_3(CN) \cdot Pr^iOH$ could be obtained. However, the reaction in 1:4 molar ratio yielded only the tri-cyano product, $Zr(OPr^i)_3(CN)_3 \cdot 3CH_3COOPr^i$.

In view of the complications caused by the isopropanol, crystalline $Zr(OPr^i)_4 \cdot Pr^iOH$ was first refluxed with cyclohexane and the adduct isopropanol was removed azeotropically. The required amount of pyruvitrile was then added in different molar ratios and the reaction mixtures were refluxed. All these reactions, can be represented as follows:

(where $n=1, m=0$; $n=2, m=0.5$; $n=3, m=1$; $n=4, m=2$).

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The mixed isopropoxy cyanides as well as zirconium tetracyanide are insoluble in common organic solvents and, therefore, their molecular weights could not be determined.

In view of the observed differences in the reactivities of titanium and zirconium tetrahalides with alcohols, it was considered worthwhile to study the reactions of these metal tetracyanides also with isopropanol. The reaction of titanium tetracyanide, $Ti(CN)_4 \cdot 1.5 CH_3COOPr^i$, with isopropanol gives the dicyanide diisopropoxide of titanium :

No coordination of either ester or isopropanol to titanium dicyanide diisopropoxide was observed. Similarly, titanium tetrabromide containing isopropyl acetate of addition, has also been reported to react with isopropanol to give the dibromide diisopropoxide³ :

On refluxing $Zr(CN)_4 \cdot 2CH_3COOPr^i$ with isopropanol, the analysis of the final products obtained corresponds to an equimolar mixture of di- and tri-cyanide derivatives of zirconium(IV) isopropoxides :

This reaction also is similar to those of zirconium tetrachloride and bromide.

Mono cyano titanium triisopropoxide shows a band at about 2175 cm^{-1} and a weak shoulder at about 2200 cm^{-1} in its infrared spectrum. In view of only one dominant peak at 2175 cm^{-1} , it can be assumed that dimerisation in the compound occurs mainly through isopropoxy bridging as depicted below :

The presence of a shoulder at 2200 cm^{-1} indicates that further weak association (as depicted by observed average molecular complexity of 2.5) may be occurring through cyanide bridging.

The monocyano zirconium triisopropoxide shows only one absorption band at about 2160 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of only terminal cyano groups. The higher cyano derivatives of titanium and zirconium show mainly three absorption bands at about 2200 ± 15 , 2150 ± 15 and $2060 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the νCN stretching region. These three bands have been assigned¹⁰⁻¹² to the bridging cyanide, terminal cyanide and terminal isocyanide forms respectively. The appearance of bands of increasing intensity at about $2200 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shows that cyanide bridgings become more important as the cyano content in these derivatives increases.

Experimental

Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Benzene, cyclohexane, ethyl alcohol, isopropanol and acetone were dried by the usual techniques. Pyruvonnitrile (Fluka) was used after distillation, b.p. 93° .

Alkoxides of titanium¹³ and zirconium¹⁴ were prepared by the standard ammonia method and purified by distillation and crystallization respectively.

Titanium and zirconium were estimated as their oxides and nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl method.

Molecular weight determinations were carried out with a semi-micro Gallenkamp Ebulliometer with thermistor sensing in refluxing benzene and acetone.

Infrared spectra in the range $4000-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer model 337 Grating spectrophotometer.

Reaction of $Ti(OPr^i)_4$ with CH_3COCN in 1:1 molar ratio :

An exothermic reaction occurred when $Ti(OPr^i)_4$ (2.42 gm, 0.008 g mole) was treated with pyruvonnitrile (0.59 gm, 0.008 g mole) in cyclohexane (~ 50 ml). The solution became yellow and turned black after some time. The reaction mixture was refluxed and the ester formed was removed azeotropically and the fractionation was continued until the boiling point of cyclohexane was reached. The reaction time was about 3 hrs. Excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. A blackish, viscous compound, which fumes on exposure to atmospheric moisture was obtained.

The reactions between $Ti(OPr^i)_4$ and CH_3COCN in other stoichiometric ratios have been carried out similarly (Table 1).

The reactions between $Zr(OPr^i)_4 \cdot Pr^iOH$ and CH_3COCN have been carried out by first removing the coordinated isopropanol azeotropically and then adding CH_3COCN in different stoichiometric ratios and refluxing the reaction mixtures (Table 2).

TABLE 1—CYANIDE DERIVATIVES OF TITANIUM(IV) ALKOXIDES

S. No.	Reactants	(g.)	Molar Ratio	Yield in gms (Calcd.)	Product (Nature).	Analysis (%)		Molecular complexity	IR assignment CN cm ⁻¹
						Found (Calcd) Ti	Found (Calcd.) N		
1.	Ti(OPr ^t) ₄ CH ₃ COCN	2.42 0.58	1:1	2.20 (2.14)	Ti(OPr ^t) ₃ (CN) black viscous	18.90 (19.10)	5.44 (5.57)	2.5*	2200 sh, 2175 m
2.	Ti(OPr ^t) ₄ CH ₃ COCN	2.84 1.38	1:2	2.43 (2.68)	Ti(OPr ^t) ₂ (CN) ₂ .0.5X (black solid)	17.74 (17.83)	10.07 (10.40)	1.00**	2220 sh, 2170 m
3.	Ti(OPr ^t) ₄ CH ₃ COCN	2.06 1.93	1:3	2.50 (2.68)	Ti(OPr ^t)(CN) ₃ .X (black solid)	16.60 (16.69)	14.93 (14.63)	1.2**	2210 sh 2160 s, 2080 m
4.	Ti(OPr ^t) ₄ CH ₃ COCN	1.86 1.80	1:4	1.99 (1.99)	Ti(CN) ₄ .1.5X (brown solid)	15.24 (15.71)	18.06 (18.36)	—	2200 m, 2150 m, 2075 w,
5.	Ti(OEt) ₄ CH ₃ COCN	3.79 1.14	1:1	3.50 (3.46)	Ti(OEt) ₃ (CN) (brown solid)	22.26 (22.92)	6.50 (6.69)	—	2160 w
6.	Ti(OEt) ₄ CH ₃ COCN	3.46 4.18	1:4	4.36 (4.30)	Ti(CN) ₄ .1.5 Y (brown solid)	16.46 (16.87)	19.51 (19.71)	—	2050 s, 2000 — 1950 d
7.	Ti(CN) ₄ .1.5X Pr ^t OH	0.62 .	1:excess	0.40 (0.41)	Ti(OPr ^t) ₂ (CN) ₂ ² (brown solid)	22.20 (21.98)	12.35 (12.84)	—	

X=CH₃COOPr^t; Y=CH₃COOEt, * Mol. wt. in benzene; ** Mol. wt. in acetone.

TABLE 2—REACTIONS OF ZIRCONIUM ISOPROPOXIDE ISOPROPONOLATE WITH PYRUVONITRILE

S. No.	Reactants	(gm)	Molar Ratio	Product (Nature)	Found (Calcd.) Zr.	Found (Calcd.) N	Assignments CN cm ⁻¹
1.	Zr(OPr ^t) ₄ .Pr ^t OH CH ₃ COCN	3.68 0.65	1:1	Zr(OPr ^t) ₃ (CN) (brown solid)	31.66 (30.99)	4.85 (4.75)	* 2160 w
2.	Zr(OPr ^t) ₄ .Pr ^t OH CH ₃ COCN	2.92 1.04	1:2	Zr(OPr ^t) ₂ (CN) ₂ .0.5X (brown solid)	29.93 (29.21)	8.53 (8.96)	2200 m 2150 w, 2075 m 2050 w,
3.	Zr(OPr ^t) ₄ .Pr ^t OH CH ₃ COCN	3.66 1.95	1:3	Zr(OPr ^t)(CN) ₃ .X (brown solid)	27.73 (27.61)	13.00 (12.71)	2200 w, 2150 w, 2080 w,
4.	Zr(OPr ^t) ₄ .Pr ^t OH CH ₃ COCN	3.37 2.40	1:4	Zr(CN) ₄ .2X (blackish brown solid)	23.02 (22.84)	14.32 (14.02)	2200 s, 2150 s, 2075 sh
5.	Zr(OPr ^t) ₄ .Pr ^t OH CH ₃ COCN	1.70 0.31	1:1	Zr(OPr ^t) ₃ (CN).Pr ^t OH** (brown solid)	25.89 (25.74)	4.06 (3.95)	
6.	Zr(OPr ^t) ₄ .Pr ^t OH CH ₃ COCN	1.75 1.26	1:4	Zr(OPr ^t)(CN) ₃ .X** (brown solid)	27.31 (27.61)	12.83 (12.71)	
7.	Zr(CN) ₄ .2X + Pr ^t OH	1.53 Excess	1:Excess	Zr(OPr ^t) ₂ (CN) ₂ .2Pr ^t OH + Zr(OPr ^t)(CN) ₃ .2Pr ^t OH (reddish solid)	25.16 (25.08)	9.36 (9.70)	

X=CH₃COOPr^t, * IR spectra in KBr pellet and other are in nuzol mull
** Reactions have been carried out at room temperature.

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